

PROBLEMS, SOLUTION AND DEVELOPMENT OF ESP IN UZBEKISTAN

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“.....as it turned out, the adventurers found a rich and fertile land. They were welcomed by the local inhabitants and they founded a new city, which they called ESP.”*
Tom Hutchinson and Alan Waters

Introduction

Until recently, in Uzbekistan, teaching English was of a general nature. English was taught in schools and institutes as a foreign language for communication. But in recent years, the attitude towards a foreign language, especially English, has changed qualitatively. A number of factors contributed to this. Firstly, the globalization of society, the introduction of new technologies and the invention of new equipment, conclusion of memorandums in the field of education on mutual exchange of students and teachers, gave a powerful impetus to the opening of educational centers for teaching foreign languages. Secondly, young people literally filled the centers. Learning English has become a top priority not only for young people, but also for scientists.

Moreover, the approach to teaching English for specific purposes has changed. Many have realized that knowledge of a language in a certain area ensures awareness of international rules and the ability to participate in international affairs, competitions and world scientific conferences.

Uzbekistan, as a country with great economic potential, has increasingly begun to attract the attention of foreign investors. The opening of economic zones and joint ventures has become another factor in deepening the study of English in our country.

Development of ESP in Uzbekistan.

Teaching of ESP in Uzbekistan underwent definite stages of development. 20-25 years ago weak knowledge of English received at school couldn't allow to realize practical value of English language.

Now, with working out new syllabi and designing materials aimed at learning specific context, taking into account learners' needs increased students' motivation and assigned responsibility on foreign language teachers teaching ESP.

Being a teacher of General English, he/she should further adapt him/herself to a new more responsible role, where he/she must muster specific terms. Besides, he/she has a task of creating new syllabi and materials, which requires special competence and knowledge.

Although, many scientists argue that the difference between ESP and EAP teachers is small, I wouldn't agree with this statement. Of course, an English teacher doesn't have enough knowledge of specific subject such as physics, maths, economics, transport, but he

possesses rich vocabulary, with the help of which he/she can easily adapt him/herself in the work with specific terms.

At the same time without needs analyses there definitely will not be any specific teaching of language as Dudley-Evans, T. & ST John M. J state “needs analysis is the process of establishing the what and how of a course”¹.As the main characters of needs analyses are people working in a specific field or profession, papers belonging to a separate occupation, employees and employers, scientists ,carrying out researches in laboratories, it is crucially for ESP practitioners to undertake the needs analyses.

In order to reveal the lack in teaching and students’needs,to direct learning of English on right rails we held survey among 100 students .The survey covered the following questions:

Survey questions	75 students	25students
1.Why do you need English?	I need it for future profession	I need it for career
	59 students	41 students
2.What are the difficulties of learning English for you?	Lack of vocabulary	Influence of word structure of native language while translating.

The teachers of English language of Bukhara engineering technological institute have enough experience of teaching ESP. Paying attention to four skills, using authentic materials at English lessons, increasing internet access, interest towards English grew considerably, communicative competence (reverse connection appeared between teachers and students) has also progressed.

Students applying to Bukhara engineering technological institute take English exams only at definite faculties or directions (like management, economics, IT).It means those, who don’t pass exam in English possess low level of English. Of course, it influences greatly on learning English with specific content.

Taking this fact into consideration we arranged their classes in the following way. First, we chose the books according their level.

Students of the first course studied English for general purposes. Students were divided into two groups according to their level. On their second year students studied more advanced course of English. Thus ,enriching their vocabulary on their third and forth courses they began to study English with special content.

We should underline that motivation of learners increased to the extent that they learn special content, they became interested in the meaning of words while translating specific texts. It became easier for them to make dialogues or conversations on topics covering their major, using specific terms and structures.

If a teacher chooses reading topics according to their general academic interests and using general career content it will help learners to develop their ability to grab other necessary skills .According to T.Dudley-Evans.“..... the skills learnt through the exercises could be transferred to the students’ own specific tasks” ² (developments in ESP p.24 T.Dudley-Evans and Maggie Jo St John.1998 Cambridge University Press)

Thus, step by step, integrating major subjects students master specific terms as well as sentence structures of technical character, which further will open them access to scientific literature on their specialization. In this way, we “help” students to be oriented in specific

literature which proves Dudley-Evans «ESP is a practical discipline with the main focus on helping students to learn³ (developments in ESP p.13 T.Dudley-Evans and Maggie Jo St John.1998 Cambridge University Press)

In my practice ,when I taught English to the third course students studying automobile industry, we learned texts which contained information about types of transport, types of engines, description of internal and external structure of automobiles.

For example, “Automobile engines must be small and light. Therefore they must run at high speed in order to get sufficient power.

Motor boats employ engines very similar to automobile engines, expect the small ones which have come into such extensive use lately - outboard motors.

Many airplane engines are of the radial air-cooled type. The word "radial" indicates that the cylinders are not arranged in line as in the typical automobile engine, but radially around a single crank.

Injection engines can be of both the four- and the two-cycle types.”⁴

In such kind of texts we don't discuss the details of engines, its detailed structure, but we get familiar with the terms of automobile with the help of which students can further work with the texts ,find proper translation or use them in written or oral speech, while translating necessary instructions on exploitation of any transport means.

As at initial courses they learnt sufficient quantity of lexical units, their vocabulary allowed them to find specific term easily. Surely, they knew their major better, and this fact helped them in correct translation and choosing necessary terms. It was very interesting for them to work with texts. I was extremely surprised when they told that they got much more information at the English lesson about types of engines as they hadn't learnt about it deeper at their major subject yet.

To reinforce what have been learnt I used short mute videos .Here students had to dub the video using the learned vocabulary. Besides, using such task as “Title the pictures” with the image of different transport means or engines also was of great use for students.

So, English teachers teach ESP if we can say so with “surface content” for informational purposes, without going into detailed studying of their major.

We just “help” them master English for their future career or independent communication while their professional occupation with the help of exercises and skills,which gradually transfer to specific level of knowledge of English language.

This is initial integration of English with their major where students learn where and how to apply possessed specific vocabulary.

That's why ,the best way to learn a foreign language is through content, when teacher does not interfere with the major subject, but teaches it with the help of the text close to the major subject.

Is collaboration necessary?

Most scientists think that special English content should be taught with collaboration of subject specialists. But opinions are different. So is mine. I don't think collaboration is necessary way in teaching specific content.

Of course we must collaborate while making syllabi and materials which must represent important elements in the teaching-learning process and must be able to influence issues such as the choice of texts which must be close to their major subjects, because English teachers don't know what topics must be covered during lessons.But team working will be waste of

time as English teachers should constantly consult with his colleague during the lesson. The best way of cooperation is before the lesson, when major subject teacher and English teacher can talk over important issues concerning teaching the forthcoming topic where difficult terms are given and demand clarification.

Let us refer to C.Barron who states: "The advantages should not obscure some of the problems associated with co-operative teaching methods. These include timetabling problems when two or more staff members need to be in the same classroom, the clashes that may occur when two very different pedagogic methods meet in the classroom, and a rapid turnover of staff necessitating the establishment of new relationships at regular intervals".⁵

Besides such collaboration may also cause definite difficulties. For example, Barron (2003) argues that "shared methodologies and shared knowledge will not necessarily lead to better learning outcomes through team teaching".⁶

That's why, the best way to learn a foreign language is through content, when teacher teaches it with the help of the text close to the major subject.

Conclusion

English teachers should choose lesson materials which cover the content of the major subject using the language comprehensible to students. That's why we seek clearer criteria for good quality teaching materials, since it has a great impact on students' learning of the language and the content. Close cooperation of major subject teachers and English teachers, sharing teaching materials, construction of the lessons with regards to students cognitive and language abilities must be priority aim of teachers. It may provide a different mindset in lesson planning and preparation. The internet and virtual environments provide great opportunities for networking with colleagues all over the world. For developing countries like Uzbekistan and many others this opportunity is the key to open the door to visit my country and share experiences.

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